

TYPES OF VRANAS AND AYURVEDIC MEDICINAL PLANTS USED FOR HEALING OF WOUNDS: REVIEW ARTICLE**Dr. Vaibhav Vasantrya Nalawade^{1*} and Dr. Amit Ramchandra Shedge²**¹P.G. Scholer, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College and Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.²Guide, Professor and HOD, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College and Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Vaibhav Vasantrya Nalawade**

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, Vranas are common problems that are primarily caused by trauma or pathologic insult and can cause patients to suffer for a long time. Healing wounds is a complicated process. Healing is an ongoing procedure for all wounds, irrespective of their type of wounds and tissue extent. The ayurvedic literature, especially the Sushruta Samhita, gives a detailed description of the etiology, pathophysiology, classification, and management of wounds. Ayurveda, a classical Indian medicinal system, includes a number of herbs, fats, oils, and minerals that have anti-aging and wound-healing qualities. Over the years, a number of plant products and phyto-active compounds have been utilized to treat wounds. Herbal extracts for wound healing promote in blood coagulation, prevent infection, and improve wound healing. In this review article, we aimed to explain various vrana types, their lakshanas, and the trying to clarify their clinical feature with list of the plants used in traditional medicine for the healing of wounds were screened. It is a beneficial work for researchers to provide many details about the wound healing herbs and development of safe and effective and globally accepted herbal drugs.

KEYWORDS: Vrana, wound, management of wounds, healing of wounds.**INTRODUCTION**

The science of life known as ayurveda is considered to have existed since the beginning of time. According to the Charak Samhita, on this globe.^[1] Human beings have been prone to injury since the beginning of existence, leading them to consider healing from an early age. Sushruta was the pioneer of Indian surgery, specifically discussed the variety of vrana types and their management in Ayurveda.^[2]

Plants have been used in traditional medicine for thousands of years and continue to offer innovative treatments.^[3] Correct knowledge of such crude drugs is crucial to the manufacture, safety, and efficacy of herbal products. Pharmacognosy is an effective technique for obtaining detailed information about crude drugs.^[4]

Definition of Vranas

Vrana Gatra Vichurnen

Vranayati iti Vrana: Su.chi 1/6^[5]

The Word 'Gatra' means tissue (connective tissue in the body or part of body)

'Vichurnane' means destruction, breaking, rupture and discontinuity of the body tissue.

Therefore, "Vrana Gatra Vichurnane" denotes phenomena complex producing tissue breaking down, rupture, or discolouration in certain parts of the body is referred to as "Vrana."

Types of Vranas**A) Sushruta specifically discussed the variety of vranas types in Ayurveda^[6]**

- 1) Nija Vrana
- 2) Aagantuja Vrana are the two main types of Vrana.

Nijavranas are caused by vitiated doshas while Aagantuja vranas are caused by external factors such as incision, punctures, laceration, poisoned cuts, bites etc. Aagantuja correlate with Sadhyo Vrana.

B) on the basis of Dosha dushti

- 1) Dushta vrana
- 2) Shuddha vrana

Classification of Nijavranas

Acharya Sushruta and Vagbhata described 15 types Nijavranas.^[7]

1. Vataja Vranas

It has a brown colour and it exudes a thin slimy cold secretion. Various type of pain like throbbing, pricking, piercing etc.

2. Pittaja Vranas

Rapid growth is the specificity of pittaja vrana. It is of yellowish colour, exudes a hot secretion resembling kimshuka flower and with burning sensation.

3. Kaphaja vrana

It has grey in colour slightly painfull, hard and feeling heaviness. It exudes a thick cold, white secretion. This type of vrana is noticed with severe itching.

4. Shonitaja vrana

This type of vrana looks like lump of red coral. It is painfull and produces a sensation of fumes escaping out. Bleeding is a notable character of this vrana. Symptoms which are seen in pittaja vrana supervene in this vrana.

5. Vatapittaja vrana

It is manifested due to vata and pitta. It is characterized by its pricking and burning pain. The colour of its secretion is same as seen in vataja and pittaja types.

6. Vatakaphaja vrana

It is characterized by severe itching, pricking pain, induration, constant discharge of cold slimy secretion.

7. Kaphapittaja

It is guru, ushna and yellow in colour. It is marked by burning sensation and it exudes a pale yellow coloured secretion.

8. Vata Shonitaja vrana

It is dry, thin, associated with piercing pain and loss of sensation. It exudes blood by the combined Doshas respective.

9. Pitta Shonitaja vrana

It is manifested by the combination of pitta and rakta. It has got the smell of fish washed water. It is soft spreading and secretes a hot blackish liquid.

10. Kaphashonitaja vrana

It is red in colour, thick, glossy and indurate. Itching and yellow colored secretion is the noticeable character of this type of vrana.

11. Vatapitta kaphaja vrana

It produces pain as if cut with a sword. Its secretion is according to each of doshas predominant.

12. Vatapitta shonitaja vrana

In this throbbing, pricking and burning pain is there. It discharges a thin yellowish fluid and produces sensation as if fumes are escaping.

13. Pitta kapha shonitaja vrana

It is of red colour. Itching, suppuration and burning sensation are found. It exudes a thick grayish blood stained secretion.

14. Vatakapha shonitaja vrana

It is marked by itching, throbbing, tingling sensation and thick grey blood stained discharge.

15. Vatapitta kapha shonitaja vrana

It is characterized by a sensation as it is burnt lacerated. It is largely sensitized by throbbing, itching, pricking and burning pain with complete loss of sensation in the affected part. Redness, suppuration, various kinds of colour, pain and secretion are its other features.

Acharaya Sushruta consider 16 types of nijavranas by adding shuddha vrana to it.

Aagantuj Vranas^[8]**1) CHINNA VRANA / Incised wound**

Wound which is oblique or straight, broad which includes falling off of the body parts is known as Chinna vrana. Chinna and Bhinna vrana are caused by sharp objects (sword, knife, axe etc.)

2) Bhinna / Punctured wound of viscera

Chest and abdominal viscera punctured by the tip of Kunta (dagger), Sakti (spear), Rasti(lance), Khadaga (sword), Vishana (horns of animals) etc. and exuding little quantity of fluids- are the features of punctured wound of the viscera.

3) Viddha / Punctured

Any part of the body except the hollow viscera, injured by the weapons or foreign bodies through small opening and making the body part bulge up even after the foreign body has come out; such a wound is to be known as Viddha vrana.

4) Kshata / Crushed

These are caused by stone, wood or any blunt objects. Wound which has neither cut the body part greatly nor the body part is punctured, but having the symptoms of both, the wound being irregular in shape and level should be appreciated as Kshata vrana.

5) Picchita / Contused

Any part of the body getting swollen, together with the bone present inside and filled with marrow and blood is known as Picchita vrana.

6) Ghrishta / Lacerated

Any part of the body losing its skin, either by assault (by weapon) or otherwise (rubbing on rough and hard surfaces etc.) accompanied with watery exudation is described as Ghrishta / abraded wound.

Agantuj Vrana said by other Acharyas in their Samhita**Ashtanghridaya: (Acharya Vagbhata)**

- 1) Ghrushta
- 2) Avakrut
- 3) Vichachinca
- 4) Pravilambita
- 5) Patita
- 6) Bhinna
- 7) Vidallita

Ashtangsangrha: (Vagbhata)^[9]**1) Chinna Vrana****Again divided in 5 Subtypes**

- 1) Ghrushta
- 2) Vichchina

- 3) Patita
- 4) Avakruta
- 5) Vilambita

2) Viddha**It again divided in 8 Subtypes**

- 1) Annuviddha
- 2) Utunndita
- 3) Atividdha
- 4) Nirviddha
- 5) Anubhinna
- 6) Bhinnotundita
- 7) Atibhinna
- 8) Nirbhinna

3) Pichchita**It again divided in subtypes.**

- 1) Savrana
- 2) Avrana

Types of Agantuj vrana according to different acharyas

Sr No.	Sushruta	Vagbhata	Sharangdhara	Ashtangsangr-aha
1	Chinna	Vicchinna	Chinna	Chinna (5) types
2	Bhinna	Bhinna	Bhinna	Pichhita
3	Viddha	Viddha	Viddha	Viddha (9) types
4	Kshataja	Awkrut	Vilambit	Avikrut
5	Pichhita	Vidalit	Ghrushtha	----
6	Ghrushtha	Ghrushtha	Prachalit	----
7	----	Pravilambit	Nipatit	----
8	----	Patita	----	----

Lakshana of Agantujvrana

Sr. No.	Type of Agantuja Vrana	Lakshana
1	Chinna (Su.Chi.2/10)	Extensive cut injury oblique or straight, separation of Parts of body.
2	Bhinna (Su.Chi.2/11)	Perforation of Asaya and milddischarge.
3	Viddha (Su.Chi.2/19)	Deep injury Without Perforation of Asaya.
4	Kshata (Su.Chi.2/20)	Neither a cut injury nor a perforation but exhibits the nature of both uneven shaped.
5	Picchita (Su.Chi.2/21)	Crushed injury extended filled with blood and Bone marrow.
6	Ghrishta (Su.Chi.2/22)	Rub injury skin gets peeled off, burning sensation and Discharge.

AYURVEDIC MEDICINAL PLANTS USED FOR HEALING OF WOUNDS^[10]

Plant-based products contribute to over 90% of ayurvedic medicines. Plant-based preparations play a major role in the ayurvedic healing process. Compared to food or spices, Ayurvedic plants have a more potent effect on the body. Through executing this, the plant can stabilize the doshas and reverse pathophysiological processes. This is why using such plants should be done properly. In Sanskrit, traditional ayurvedic remedies made from these plants are referred to as "yoga." Years of practical application combining plants to achieve the best results led to the formation of yoga.

Additionally, polyherbal formulations have shown longer-lasting efficacy than individual plants. The majority of traditional ayurvedic remedies are polyherbal, combining three to thirty different herbs. The correct combination of these ingredients results in a balanced and reproducible composition. In certain combinations, one or two of the plants will be active while the rest will only be supporting. Each of the supporting herbs will function differently, serving as a catalyst to promote appropriate absorption, facilitate transportation, and minimize toxicity. Superior outcomes are possible if the right combination is provided, however these results depend on a comprehensive understanding of plants.

LIST OF MEDICINAL PLANTS USED FOR HEALING OF WOUNDS^[11-22]

Sr No.	Drug Name	Latine Name	Family	Part Used
1	Acacia catechu Wild	Khair	Mimosaceae	Bark
2	Aegle marmelos	Bael	Rutaceae	Root
3	Aloe vera (L.) Burm. f.	Korphad	Liliaceae	Leaf juice
4	Azadirachta indica Juss	Neem	Meliaceae	Leaves
5	Calotropi sprocera (Ait.)R. Br.	Rui	Asclepiadaceae	Leaves and Latex
6	Centella asiatica	Brahmi	Umbelliferae	Flowers
7	Colocasia esculenta (L.)Schott	Alu	Araceae	Leaf extract
8	Commiphora mukul Hook	Guggule	Burseraceae	Whole plant
9	Curcuma longa	Halad	zingiberaceae	Rhizome, Seeds
10	Dauca scarota L.	Gajar	Apiaceae	Root
11	Eucalyptus globules	Eucalyptus	Myrtaceae	Oil
12	Lawsonia innermisalba L.	Mehdi	Lythraceae	Leaves, Seeds, Bark and Flowers
13	Neumbo nuciera	Kamal	Nymphaeaceae	Rhizomes
14	Ocimum sanctum L.	Tulsi	Labiatae	Leaves
15	Phyllanthus embilica	Amla	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit
16	Terminalia arjuna	Arjun	Combretaceae	Bark
17	Terminalia chebula	Myrobalan harda	Combretoreceae	Leaves & fruit
18	Trigonella foenum graecum L	Methi	Fabaceae	Seeds
19	Withania somnifera Dunal.	Ashwagandha	AshwagandhaSol anaceae	Root, Seeds
20	Zingiber officinale Rosc	Adrak	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
21	Picrorhiza kurroa	Kutki	Plantaginaceae	Leaf, bark, Rhizomes
22	Symplocosa racemos	Lodhra	Symplocaceae	Bark
23	Myrica esculanta	Kayphal	Myricaceae	Bark
24	Glycyrrhiza glabra	Mulethi	Fabaceae	Root
25	Rubia cordifolia	Manjitha	Rubiaceae	Root

CONCLUSION

According to the overview above, different Acharayas in Ayurveda have characterized vranas and their different types. To determine the most effective type of therapy for a wound, a clinician should be able to identify the phase at which the wound is healing. Traditional Ayurvedic practices can effectively prevent a great deal of suffering and disability if a wound is properly assessed and treated.

The majority of the natural plants in this assessment have the ability to heal wounds. Because they naturally promote the healing mechanism, plants are more effective healers. Herbal medications are becoming more and more popular in both developed and developing nations due to its increased safety and well-tolerated nature. Compared to those allopathic medications. To confirm these plants' efficacy, studies with humans and animals should be conducted.

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